

PAK-US RELATIONS DURING PRESIDENT BIDEN ERA (2021-2025): AN ANALYSIS

^{*1}Dr. Adnan Nawaz, ²Hafiz Muhammad Bilal

^{*1}Assistant Professor, Department of International Relations, Government College University, Faisalabad.

²MPhil, Department of International Relations, Government College University, Faisalabad.

^{*1}adnannawaz@gcuf.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Adnan Nawaz

Abstract

This article deals with the conundrums of Pak-US relations during Biden administration. Pak-US ties remained at a somewhat low level throughout the four-year period of the presidency of Joe Biden, not because of a genuine rift but more because of the White House's seeming lack of interest. Despite sending a brief letter to Pakistan's prime minister following the country's contentious 2024 election, Biden departs office as the president of the United States to have never phoned with his counterpart in Pakistan. This minimal stability for both countries is mostly a reflection of Pakistan's diminished significance to the US following the conclusion of the Afghan War. Into the upcoming administration, that will persist. Drawing from qualitative methodology, the article tends to explain the waxes and wanes of the US-Pakistan ties.

Introduction

The fact that the United States wants to build lasting connections with the newly elected government in Pakistan meanwhile also putting pressure on them to use their authority with Taliban to meet international demands, it is evident that the area of relationship between the two countries is somewhat narrow and centered around security. Joe Biden's failure to contact Khan after taking office irritated him as PM and became a point of conflict, which caused the Pakistan-US relationship to immediately deteriorate. When the United States left Afghanistan in August 2021, Islamabad became relevant to its foreign policy goals again, but at this point mostly within the lens of security at its borders and the fight against terrorism which remains the case to the present time. Following its departure from Afghanistan, the administration of Joe Biden shifted its attention to strategic rivalry with China in Asia, keeping Pakistan, which has economic ties to China, at a distance from it.

Khan further criticized the United States of openly pressuring Pakistan to join its purported WoT, that resulted in approximately eighty thousand fatalities and about \$123 billion in economic damages. The rising animosity involving the administration of Joe Biden and the then-prime minister Khan made the United States an easy scapegoat when Imran lost the motion of no confidence (Lodhi et al., 2022). Pak-US relationship has suffered several losses over the four years of Biden government, chief among them being the Taliban takeover and the withdrawal from Afghanistan. In its approach to Pakistan, the Biden administration has now chosen a bureaucratic division of labor: ongoing military and security contacts; a strong, clearly defined meeting from the State Department; and a lack of involvement from the White House. Below are some ways that the present asymmetry is different from previous ones: In recent memory, neither Khan nor Sharif, the prime of Pakistan, have had any interactions with President Joe Biden. Moreover, the two nations are attempting to broaden their ties, something that is noteworthy as it is no longer largely focused on the US's objectives in Afghanistan as it was before their withdrawal (Afzal, 2023).

Since the PML-N and President Biden have a good connection, they will likely keep using their ties in Washington to patch up their strained ties. Robust military institution of Pakistan, that seeks to maintain an equilibrium between ties with the US and China, would likewise support and collaborate on such activities. In stark opposition to Khan's anti-American

rhetoric, then army chief emphasized Pakistan's important and enduring tactical ties with the United States during the April 2023 Islamabad Security Dialogue.

Pak-US Relations: A Strained and Complex Beginning

Under President Joe Biden's leadership, the USA and Pakistan's relationship deteriorated compared to earlier decades due to a significant drop in high-level involvement, changing objectives, and a transactional strategy. Joe didn't directly interact with leadership of Pakistan, in contrast to previous presidents of the United States, which was indicative of Washington's waning strategic interest in Pakistan after the USA withdrew from Afghanistan (Afzal, 2023).

A notable change in the USA's geopolitical interests was reflected in government of Joe Biden strategy regarding Pakistan, which was characterized by a conspicuous absence of a high-level interaction. President Biden didn't call then PM Imran Khan or his successor Shahbaz Sharif once all through his tenure. Pakistan's diminishing significance in the FP of the USA, especially in the wake of America's departure from Afghanistan, was made abundantly evident by this extraordinary quiet.

When Biden called Pakistan "one of the most dangerous nations in the world" in a political rally in October 2022, relations took a bad turn (Lodhi, 2022). The White House was later forced to emphasize that the United States cherished its mutually beneficial alliance with Pakistan after his remarks concerning Pakistan's political instability and nuclear capability caused fury in Pakistan. But the harm had already been inflicted; the comment confirmed the idea that the administration of Joe Biden saw Pakistan more as an issue than an ally.

A number of reasons contributed to this cooling of ties. Despite Islamabad's involvement in promoting peace, Washington was extremely wary of Pakistan's relations to the Taliban following the tense American pullout from Afghanistan. Despite ongoing counterterrorism collaboration, which included a 450 million-dollar agreement to keep the country's F-16 aircraft in service, the relationship shifted from being strategic to being purely transactional (Iqbal, 2022). Tight links of Islamabad to Beijing made it less desirable as a partner, while the United States had evidently turned its priority to fortifying ties with India as an alternative to China.

According to observers, Pak-US ties reached a "low-level equilibrium" by the conclusion of Biden's tenure, which maintained the required military and counterterrorism collaboration but lacked the warmth and depth of earlier decades (Vestenskov, 2024). Economic difficulties

of Pakistan and geopolitical location, together with the lack of presidential involvement, indicated that the ties seemed probably going to stagnate for the foreseeable future without a significant crisis or strategic shift. A permanent reevaluation of Pakistan's position in American foreign policy goals may have resulted from this chilly start under Biden, rather than merely a brief deterioration in relations.

Virtual Climate Summit and the US Invitation

After being left out of a recent virtual climate meeting, the United States extended an invitation to Pakistan to join. The invitation emphasized the importance of the involvement of Pakistan in global climate negotiations, particularly given the country's vulnerability to the consequences of changes in the climate. The summit aims to bring together several countries to collaborate on climate action and share strategies for mitigating the effects of global warming. This move could signify a renewed commitment to international environmental cooperation. At the April 2021 Climate Leaders summit, Pakistan made a number of important statements regarding its position on the issue of climate change, sustainable development, and the need for close collaboration between developed and developing countries in order to combat climate change while enlisting the help of other countries (Hussain, 2024).

Summit for Democracy

In March 2023, the second edition of the Summit for Democracy took place. The global summit of democracies did not include a number of democratic countries from Asia and Africa; some were not invited, while others turned down the invitation. Highlighting solely bilateral ties of Pakistan with the USA, an important ally, Pakistan declined to travel. Some scholars think that the real reason for Pakistan's absence was not democracy but China. "This was a rather clear diplomatic choice," added Michael Kugelman, chairman of the Wilson Center's South Asia section, "China was not invited, but Taiwan was. "Out of respect for its Chinese ally, Pakistan would not want to attend a forum where Taiwan was present" (Dawl, 2023).

The Afghanistan Withdrawal and Its Aftermath

Although the USA's longest war came to an end in August 2021 with the US's departure, the chaotic execution and immediate fallout seriously tarnished the United States reputation, weakened the region, and brought Afghanistan in Taliban authority with grave security and humanitarian ramifications. The Doha accord between The USA and Taliban, that included a withdrawal deadline of May 2021, was passed down to the Biden government. Biden

continued with the retreat, prolonging it up to September of 2021, regardless of intelligence concerns. The United States authorities were taken off surprise by the swift disintegration of Afghan security forces, who had depended on American air assistance and logistical. When the Taliban took control of Kabul in mid-August 2021, Hamid Karzai International Airport (HKIA) had to be evacuated quickly (U.S. Government, 2024).

Chaos plagued the evacuation attempt. Because HKIA was the only exit when the United States prematurely closed Bagram Air Base, it formed a bottleneck. Although offering surrounding protection, the Taliban were unable to stop an ISIS-K terrorist attack on the 26th of August 2021, which killed approximately 170 Afghans and 13 U.S. servicemen. Ten people, including children, were accidentally murdered in a follow-up the United States drone strike that was meant to stop another assault (Olay, 2024). Twenty years of advancements in rights for women, schooling, and administration were undone by the Taliban's comeback to authority. Strict sharia rule, which included floggings and public executions, was reinstated, women were prohibited from most employment, and girls were prohibited from attending high school.

Pakistan's Domestic Politics and U.S. Perceptions

The Biden administration's internal political unrest in Pakistan had a big impact on how the United States saw the nation and strengthened increasing distance of Washington from Islamabad. The United States administration responded to the period's democratic backsliding, military control over civilian governance, and the contentious detention of former Prime Minister Imran Khan in a subdued but revealing manner. The administration of Joe Biden refrained from openly criticizing Khan's treatment in spite of these difficulties, demonstrating a practical emphasis on preserving counterterrorism collaboration with military of Pakistan. While Khan's court challenges became a focal point for human rights-minded the United States politicians, the United States ambassador's rapid interaction with Sharif's administration suggested approval of the current quo. Strategic importance of Pakistan importance to Washington was further reduced by its economic instability, which was characterized by IMF bailouts and skyrocketing debt (Arab News, 2024).

In keeping with a larger tendency of tying help to adherence Pakistan to Western security and financial demands, the United States used its authority at the IMF to pressure for changes. The Biden administration exposed a glaring difference between interests of Pakistan and the USA. The USA's disregard for Pakistan's goals of democracy and its sole concentration

on combating terrorism and nuclear stability reduced the partnership to a transactional alliance, despite Islamabad's efforts to strike a balance between its relations with China and the United States (Mohan, 2024). Despite its disruptive political involvement, the United States' continued dependence on the military of Pakistan implies that security considerations will take precedence over democratic governance for the foreseeable future.

Strategic and Economic Shifts: To Geo-Economics from Geopolitics

Throughout the Biden administration, there was a notable but ultimately fruitless endeavor to move the Pak-US ties away from its conventional security-centric paradigm and toward economic cooperation. Reciprocal need led to this geoeconomic shift: the United States aimed to offset China's influence in the area through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), while Pakistan sought to shed its "frontline state" character associated with the conflicts in Afghanistan. Nevertheless, any significant change was thwarted by systemic barriers and conflicting goals. The Pak-US "Green Alliance" concept, which was unveiled in 2023 and aimed to replace the Cold War-era security alliance with collaboration on climate change, agriculture, and energy, was at the center of this attempted transition (Butt & Askari, 2023).

Technical support for renewable energy projects and Pakistan's water management issues, especially in Sindh region which was devastated by floods, was offered by the program. At the same time, Washington urged American businesses to investigate Pakistan's vital natural resources, such as the excellent lithium mines in Baluchistan that the United States Geological Survey had identified as a possible substitute for supply networks controlled by China. There were immediate obstacles to these commercial overtures. Substantial American private investment was discouraged by Pakistan's ongoing balance of payments problems and dependence on IMF bailouts. The ability of Pakistan to fund significant infrastructure projects was constrained by the strict terms of the \$3 billion IMF program that was authorized in 2023 (IMF, 2023). Furthermore, workers from China at BRI projects were regularly targeted by separatists, and the safety circumstance in mineral-rich Balochistan remained unstable. Barring significant assurances from the government that the administration of Joe Biden declined to offer, US companies have shown a reluctance to take on similar dangers.

This economic shift's strategic component presented similar challenges. Pakistan continues to extend the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), particularly delicate investments like the port of Gwadar growth, even as it openly embraced the formation of the

Green Coalition. Pakistan anticipated America would rival Beijing's free funding while keeping strategic ties with China, which secretly infuriated US officials (Younus, 2021). When the nation's military turned down American plans for alternate port expansion in Karachi out of concern that it would lessen influence of China in Gawadar, this conflict became glaring.

The Indo-Pacific policy of the administration of Joe Biden made things much more difficult. Due to non-proliferation concerns, Pakistan's demands for comparable technology transfers were denied while Washington strengthened its defense and technology connections with India through programs like the iCET (Indo-U.S. Critical and Emerging Technology) collaboration (The White House, 2025). Due to the United States Trade Representative Katherine Tai's refusal to negotiate with Pakistan in the Indo-Pacific Economic Framework (IPEF) discussions, the much-discussed Trade and Investment Framework Agreement (TIFA) discussions continued to stagnate (US Trade Representative, 2024). The geo-economic project was mostly a failure by 2024. With the \$100 million Green Alliance commitment mostly unmet, U.S. development aid to Pakistan fell to its lowest level since 2001 (U.S. Missions Pakistan, 2024). State owned companies from China surpassed American companies for Baluchistan's research rights, the lithium extraction project fell apart. In cables that were released, Pakistan's acting commerce minister acknowledged that the nation had "no credible alternative" to investments from China, and U.S. officials came to the conclusion that Pakistan lacked the economic stability necessary to be an honest competitor in logistics expansion.

Afghanistan Security and Peace

The "implied" and "relevance" (Gul, 2020) justifications remained the cornerstones of U.S. foreign policy regarding Pakistan. Even after the withdrawal of US troops from Afghanistan, Pakistan remains a significant player in the debate. Strategic importance of India and geostrategic collaboration of Pakistan with China in the wake of its escalating anti-US sentiment were among the proposed elements. By applying pressure to the Taliban, Pakistan has played a crucial role in the discussions for the Doha Peace Agreement between the United States and the Taliban. The final settlement agreements were the entire responsibility of the United States and Taliban negotiators, with no participation from Pakistan or others. Taliban committed to provide assurances that no organization or individuals was going to utilize Afghan territory to jeopardize the security of the United States and its allies in return for an intra-Afghan settlement and the withdrawal of American forces in fourteen months.

The agreement makes it quite evident that democratic framework and stability of Afghanistan were given little more than a cursory mention. A wise plan for a sustainable peace in Afghanistan should have included regional players including Pakistan, Iran, Russia and China. Despite his initial skepticism, Biden decided to back the Doha Accord given the timeline for the United States military pullout. In retrospect, it is easy to recognize that the United States armed forces, intelligence, and policy planners misjudged the Taliban's ability to wage war and the strength and capabilities of the 300,000-strong Afghan National Army (ANA), which they had been training for years (Shea, 2021). Kabul has been overrun by the Taliban in less than a month. Despite the fact that, as Biden stated, the United States spent \$1 trillion (\$1.34 trillion) on education and encouraging them and continuously provided them with support from the air, transportation, and compensation, the ANA, the backbone of the shunned Ashraf Ghani leadership, surrendered at all legally binding residences and even did not resist (Bashir, Naseer & Majeed, 2025).

The Afghan situation is Pakistan's biggest foreign policy dilemma! If the United States and its citizens view the withdrawal of soldiers from Afghanistan as a defeat for the United States, it may be easily passed on to Pakistan as Taliban sympathizers, creating tension with the Biden government. Pakistan no longer has the same sway over the Taliban as it once had, despite what many Westerners believe. The capitulation of almost all of Afghanistan and the departure of US troops has also been gradually undermining its impact.

If it possessed so much influence, might it not have attempted to sever the Taliban's links to Tehreek e Taliban Pakistan? Pakistan and the United States are concerned about projecting a sense of US success in Afghanistan after 2,480 American deaths and over US\$2 trillion (\$2.73 trillion) in monetary costs during the course of twenty years (Shea, 2021). On the flip side, Pakistan-US ties might stay marred by the shame of an American failures. Peace driven by Afghan was essential to Pakistan's efforts to boost regional commerce, handle domestic terrorism, and build its fragile economy. Despite the USA's short-term memory, acceptance by Biden, that avoids blaming Pakistan and instead criticizes the Afghan National Army (ANA) for not opposing the Taliban, is encouraging for resolving any future conflicts (Bashir, Naseer & Majeed, 2025). The United States and Pakistan frequently hold identical opinions regarding Kabul, despite their different tactics. This distrust may be resolved by continuing to communicate at the military and political levels.

Foreign policy of the USA imperatives that require that Islamabad be assessed by considering its interactions with both India and China are the reason for Pakistan's conviction that Washington will both diminish and distort Islamabad's significance. Because of the the United States abandonment of the periphery after the Soviet Union left Afghanistan and the economic penalties that followed, as well as an adversarial neighbor to the east, Pakistan was forced to turn toward Chinese.

US Response to Turmoil in Pakistan

Even if the United States and Pakistan seem to be getting along better, the US will be careful not to put too much of a wall between the two countries in order to reach a compromise because of Pakistan's growing political unrest and strong widespread backing for Imran Khan. The crackdown on party of the nation's previous leader of government, Imran Khan, has made the United States hesitant to respond to the instability in politics in Pakistan. America had yet to express real concerns about the ongoing turmoil in Pakistan, with the exception of early remarks by the State Department and Congresswoman Sheila Jackson Lee, the chair and founding member of the Congressional Pakistan Caucus in the United States Congress. The silence from the Biden administration implies that the United States has chosen to avoid any potential conflict establishment. The USA was likewise conscious that the country's civilian governments are subordinate to the country's powerful military establishment (Mishra & Sharma, 2023). Because of this, the United States feels more at ease working with army of Pakistan on matters related to defense, such as cooperation on counterterrorism and advancements in Afghanistan.

Bilateral Security Ties

Extent of Pak-US security cooperation was already diminishing before to the USA's military and diplomatic withdrawal from Afghanistan. There is still little bilateral cooperation, mainly in the areas of security in the region and countering terrorism. The two trips to Pakistan by the Commander of the USA's Central Command in 2022, the October 2022 Pentagon reception for Chief of army of Pakistan hosted by the United States Secretary of Defense, and the March 2023 U.S.-Pakistan Counterterrorism Negotiation are examples of a high degree military contacts. The only source of security-related aid for Pakistan since their reinstatement in 2021 has been funding for International Narcotics Control and Law Enforcement (Blinken, 2022).

In July 2022, Ayman al-Zawahri, the leader of al Qaida, was killed by a US drone attack in Kabul, Afghanistan. Afghan Taliban officials accused Pakistan of supplying an airbase for the operation right after it took place (Fazl-e-Haider, 2022). Many experts believe that Pakistan must have been aware of the strike and likely approved of it before it could have occurred, despite of strong denials of any participation by Pakistan government.

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China Factor

A relational database developed by the "Stockholm International Peace Research Institute" shows that in 2021, Pakistan bought more than \$750 million worth of weaponry from Beijing. In the very first half of March 2022, air force of Pakistan debuted its first batch of J-10C fighter aircraft. Although officials from Pakistan government have formerly indicated as many as twenty-five airplanes in press sources, Pakistan has not disclosed the exact number of aircraft purchased under the arrangement (Mathews & Anicetti, 2024). Military of Pakistan has continued to be a consistent buyer of Chinese munitions. However, it also used to purchase from the USA. China and Pakistan, longtime regional partners, have lately strengthened their commerce, investments, and economic relations. Former Prime Minister of Pakistan Khan, had been in the city to execute agreements in a variety of areas, such as as ethics, digitalization, solar, and technical assistance, during the official opening ceremony of the Olympic Games in Beijing.

Pak-China ties were examined by Michele Kugelman, a specialist in South Asian issues: In contrast to its at best precarious ties with the USA, interaction of Pakistan with China is on the rise. In a conversation with Wilson Center, Prime Minister's special advisor Moeed Yousuf, stated that we would want to begin by talking about investment connections. In Washington, the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) debate is not always amicable. What if US-based businesses arrived, invested, reconditioned products for export purposes, and then sent them to whichever location they wanted? Why not seek business ventures in which China, the United States of America, and Pakistan might pool their resources? Close

links of Pakistan to China are one of the most important factors in the improvement of relations involving Islamabad and Washington. Increasing dependency of Pakistan on China for its defense and economic requirements had an impact on the USA's choice to approve the F-16 fighter jet acquisition (Tasci, 2022).

Some analysts in Washington and New Delhi think China is working with Pakistan to curtail India's might, and China has provided diplomatic support for Pakistan's foreign policy and Kashmir position. As an ardent critic of China, Biden believes that the United States and China will keep competing and that they ought to encourage India to form strategic partnerships with them. That does not mean that the United States has given up on Pakistan. In the current budget, the United States has set aside possibly tens of millions of dollars for aid to Pakistan, with the majority going to the education and health sectors. The US\$13.8 million (S\$18.55 million) allocated for regional Transnational Army Training and Education would also help Pakistan (Younus, 2023). Although the United States and Pakistan have both made unpleasant remarks recently, neither country appears to be interested in a long-term split. Regarding this, Kugelman stated, "It might be incorrect to imply that Pak-US relationship is coming to an end because of Pakistan's strengthening ties with China and expanding alliances with other adversaries of the United States. Islamabad is still open to a certain level of collaboration.

Conclusion

Pakistan cannot effectively go from being a geopolitical pawn to a geoeconomic partner until it addresses basic concerns about governance, security, and macroeconomic stability. Although both countries acknowledged that they needed to shift from their post-9/11 framework, the Biden years showed that neither was prepared or willing to make the required concessions to establish a fresh economic basis for the partnership. Because of this, the relationships continued to be confined inside the well-known structure regarding cooperation in security, but with dwindling benefits for both parties. A major change in Pak-US ties was highlighted by the Biden administration: from an alliance of urgency to an arrangement of confined, pragmatic involvement. The partnership was expected to stagnate in the absence of a significant geopolitical stimulus, such as a resumption of the Afghan conflict or a détente between the United States and China aided by Pakistan. Only possibility for Pakistan to regain interest of

Washington may be to expand its relationships beyond security and take advantage of economic prospects.

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